

Clinical case study

Ageing from a Traditional Chinese Medicine Perspective: A Case Study.

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Abstract

Introduction: Ageing is a multifactorial process involving physiological, cognitive, and emotional changes. From a Traditional Chinese Medicine perspective, this process is understood as a natural decline of Essence (*Jing*), primarily associated with Kidney *Yin* deficiency and energetic imbalances among internal organs. Integrative therapeutic approaches such as acupuncture, phytotherapy, diet therapy, *Tui Na*, and *Qigong* have been used to promote energetic balance and improve the quality of life of older adults.

Objective: To evaluate the effects of Traditional Chinese Medicine-based therapies, including acupuncture, phytotherapy, diet therapy, *Tui Na*, and *Qigong* practices, on managing physical and emotional symptoms related to ageing through a clinical case study.

Methods: This report details the clinical follow-up of a 69-year-old male patient presenting with symptoms of anxiety, memory loss, and irritability. His conventional diagnosis was hypertension, for which he was on daily medication. The Traditional Chinese Medicine diagnosis indicated Kidney *Yin* and Fluid Deficiency with Ascendant *Yang*. The treatment plan included 10 weekly, individualised acupuncture sessions, complemented by phytotherapy, diet therapy, *Tui Na* massage, and *Qigong* exercises. The results were assessed through a self-evaluation questionnaire and clinical observation during the sessions.

Results: A significant anxiety reduction was observed, along with improved sleep quality, mental clarity, and a decrease in headaches. While some mild forgetfulness persisted, the patient developed effective compensatory strategies, such as noting appointments and daily activities in a notebook. The patient also showed notable improvement in emotional management, with reduced irritability and a more compassionate attitude towards his own limitations.

Conclusion: The integrative Traditional Chinese Medicine approach demonstrated potential for improving emotional and cognitive symptoms associated with ageing, suggesting benefits for the patient's quality of life. The synergistic effect of combining multiple therapies proved beneficial. Further controlled studies are necessary to confirm these results and to validate the role of Traditional Chinese Medicine in promoting harmonious ageing.

Keywords: Acupuncture; Phytotherapy; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Kidney *Yin* Deficiency; Rising *Yang*; Memory Loss.

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1. Introduction

According to conventional medicine, ageing is a process of cellular decline that occurs over time ¹. It is a complex and multifactorial process, and there are several variables that can promote or delay this ageing. These factors can be genetic, but also biopsychosocial, related to nutrition, physical exercise habits, clinical conditions, and the social environment, as well as the way a person responds to daily challenges, stress, and conflicts ^{2,3}.

"Old age is therefore the stage where the decline of bodily functions and various changes in systems and organs occur" ⁴.

In Traditional Chinese Medicine, ageing is understood as a natural process associated with the progressive decline of the *Jing*, stored in the kidneys ^{5,6}. This essence is the basis of vitality, growth, development, and reproduction, being directly related to longevity and the general state of physical and mental health ⁷⁻⁹. As age progresses, a physiological decrease in the functions of the internal organs (*Zang Fu*) is expected, especially the kidneys, which control the bones, marrow, and the brain's fundamental structures for cognition, emotional balance, and vital force ^{6,10}.

In addition to the physical aspect, Traditional Chinese Medicine recognises that ageing is deeply linked to the emotional sphere. The emotional wear and tear accumulated throughout life, as well as unresolved traumas, can contribute to energetic imbalances that manifest through psychological and somatic symptoms, affecting the individual's quality of life ^{8,10}.

In this context, anxiety, irritability, persistent sadness, and other emotional states are seen not only as psychological manifestations but also as signs of energetic disharmony between the internal organs, especially the heart, liver, spleen, and kidneys ¹¹. An integrative approach based on Traditional Chinese Medicine can, therefore, offer a holistic and personalised approach, respecting the uniqueness of each individual in the ageing process ¹².

The World Health Organization estimates that there are 47.5 million individuals with dementia worldwide, a number that could reach 75.6 million in 2030 and nearly triple to 135.5 million by 2050.

Alzheimer's disease holds a prominent place in this context, accounting for about 60 to 70% of all dementia cases ^{13,14}. According to the American Psychiatric Association, dementias are syndromes characterised by cognitive decline, loss of intellectual skills, and consciousness that affects the social and professional domain of the individual in question ¹.

2. Case Presentation

A 69-year-old male patient sought consultation with a five-year history of anxiety, memory complaints, irritability, chest pressure, and morning headaches. Also reported non-restorative sleep, with frequent disturbing dreams, occasional difficulty falling asleep, and a sense of fatigue upon waking.

The patient had a conventional diagnosis of hypertension and was under daily anti-hypertensive medication.

To monitor the patient's progress, a symptom self-evaluation questionnaire was applied at the first and last consultations in order to compare the results and understand the effectiveness of the treatment.

The Traditional Chinese Medicine diagnosis indicated Kidney *Yin* and Fluid Deficiency with Ascendant *Yang*, a pattern manifesting as a combination of *Yin* deficiency symptoms (e.g., dry throat, night sweats, restlessness, insomnia) and *Yang* hyperactivity (e.g., irritability, headaches, dizziness). The treatment plan was designed to address these specific imbalances.

In addition, the team referred to the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-11)¹⁵, developed by the World Health Organization (WHO), which provides standardised criteria for diagnosis within the Traditional Chinese Medicine framework (Table 1)

Table 1: Description for Kidney *Yin* deficiency according to ICD-11 codes.

Code	Description
SD83 Restlessness disorder (MT1)	Disorder characterised by restlessness or sadness. It can be explained by emotional factors, postpartum, <i>yin</i> blood deficiency, long-term accumulation of fire or heat, depletion of congenital essence, imbalance of <i>Yin</i> and <i>Yang</i> , or disturbance of <i>Qi</i> activity.

SD23 Forgetfulness disorder (MT1)	Disorder characterised by partial or total memory loss. It can be explained by dysfunction of the cardiac or splenic system, senility, accumulation of phlegm, or blood stasis.
SD87 Repressed fire disorder (MT1)	Disorder characterised by a sensation of heat, congestion, dry mouth, anxiety, depression, irritability, headache, dizziness, loss of appetite, or epigastric distension. It can be explained by chronically repressed anger, inducing mental and physical symptoms.
SF58 Pattern of flaming and ascending liver fire (MT1)	Pattern characterised by fever, thirst, headache, dizziness, restlessness, insomnia, red, sore, and swollen eyes, sudden tinnitus or deafness, or bright red blood from the upper body (nose or mouth, from coughing or vomiting), irritability, bitter taste, reddened skin, red tongue with a yellow coating, and rapid and strong pulse. It can be explained by the hyperactivity of excess liver fire flaming upwards to the head or tissues associated with the hepatic system.
SF93 Kidney <i>yin</i> deficiency pattern (MT1)	Pattern characterized by pain and weakness in the waist and knees, insomnia, dizziness, ringing in the ears, nocturnal emission in men and infrequent or light menstruation in women, emaciation, dry throat, thirst, flushed cheeks, dysphoria with a febrile sensation in the palms of the hands, soles of the feet, and chest region, afternoon fever, night sweats, red tongue with a scant coating, and a rapid and weak pulse. It can be explained by kidney <i>yin</i> deficiency that leads to the interior disturbance of fire originating from <i>yin</i> deficiency.
SF10 Fluid deficiency pattern (MT1)	Pattern characterised by a dry mouth and throat, chapped lips and cracks at the corners of the mouth, dry skin, thirst with a desire to drink, scanty urination, dry bowel movements, a red and dry tongue, and a thin, rapid, and weak pulse. It can be explained by insufficient bodily fluids that cannot moisten and nourish the body's organs and tissues.
SG64 Middle <i>yin</i> stage pattern (MT1)	Pattern characterised by a desire to lie down or rest, cold limbs, diarrhoea, dysphoria, a desire to sleep, a rapid and thin pulse, or a thin and weak pulse. It can be explained by moderate cold in the inner layer of the body.

3. Interventions

A 10-session weekly treatment plan was implemented. The first five sessions used the same protocol, while the last five were adjusted based on the patient's evolving symptoms. *Tui Na* was used to complement the treatment in the sessions. The patient also received complementary support at home through *Qigong*, phytotherapy, and diet therapy prescription.

3.1. Acupuncture

Acupuncture, one of the main therapies of Traditional Chinese Medicine, consists of inserting thin needles into specific points located in the energetic meridians, with the objective of re-establishing the balance of *Qi* (vital energy) and promoting the body's homeostasis¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Several studies indicate that acupuncture exerts regulatory effects on the central nervous system, modulating neurotransmitters and increasing cerebral perfusion, which can justify benefits in the cognition and mood of the elderly¹⁹⁻²¹. In Table 2, the points and meridians used in the treatment sessions are presented.

Table 2. Acupuncture points and meridians used in the treatment sessions, as well as the treatment procedure.

1 st to 5 th sessions	
Point/meridian	Procedure
KI3 (<i>Taixi</i>)	Check for the most sensitive R3 point; the most sensitive one determines the side to be needled initially.
Kidney Meridian	Palpate the channel up to the knee and needle all sensitive Ashi points to promote global balance.
Bladder Meridian	On the contralateral Bladder channel, needling Ashi points to promote global balance. Points in the posterior area (less accessible) should be needled with the leg flexed, stimulating the point using one of the techniques until <i>DeQi</i> is reached. Remove the needle and place the limb in a comfortable position.

Lung Meridian	Ipsilateral to the Bladder meridian, contralateral to the Kidney, needling Ashi points to promote global balance.
Large Intestine Meridian	Ipsilateral to the Kidney, contralateral to the Lung and Bladder, needling the Ashi points to promote global balance.
Liver Meridian	Ipsilateral to the Kidney and Large Intestine, needling the Ashi points to promote global balance.
Stomach Meridian	Ipsilateral to the Bladder and Lung channels, needling the Ashi points to promote global balance.
Du Mai 20 (<i>Baihui</i>)	Improves mental clarity and reduces headaches.
<i>Yintang</i>	Pacifies internal wind.
Ren Mai 17 (<i>Shanzhong</i>)	Opens the chest, tonifies and regulates Lung <i>Qi</i> , and subdues rebellious Lung <i>Qi</i> .
6th to 10th sessions	
Point	Indications
HT7 (<i>Shenmen</i>)	Calm the <i>Shen</i> and improve sleep.
PC6 (<i>Neiguan</i>)	Calms the mind and relieves emotional tension.
Du Mai 20 (<i>Baihui</i>)	Improves mental clarity and reduces headaches.
SP6 (<i>Sanyinjiao</i>)	Nourishes the blood, calms the mind, and harmonises the Spleen.
Li4 (<i>Hegu</i>)	Alleviate pain, regulate the flow of <i>Qi</i> and Blood, and support the body's natural functions, especially in the head and intestines.
GB20 (<i>Fengchi</i>)	Treats headaches and improves circulation in the brain.
KI3 (<i>Taixi</i>)	Tonifies, nourishes, and strengthens the Kidney function.
ST36 (<i>Zusanli</i>)	Tonifies <i>Qi</i> and Blood, harmonises and strengthens the Spleen and Stomach, and strengthens the body and <i>Wei Qi</i> .
SP10 (<i>Xuehai</i>)	Tonifies the blood and improves mental clarity.

3.2. *Tui Na*

Tui Na is a therapeutic technique from Traditional Chinese Medicine that uses manual manipulations on meridians and acupuncture points to promote energetic balance, relieve muscle pain, improve the circulation of *Qi* and blood, and restore the function of internal organs^{22,23}.

In this case, gliding movements were performed along the Bladder and Gallbladder channels (descending) to counteract the ascension of *Yang*. Pressure was applied to the kidney area to tonify it, and a movement of shaking the lower limbs was used to promote *Qi* harmonisation, relax the nervous system, and improve circulation²⁴.

3.3. *Qigong*

Qigong is a Chinese therapeutic practice that combines gentle movements, controlled breathing, and mental concentration to cultivate and regulate *Qi*, promoting health, preventing diseases, and balancing body and mind^{25,26}.

The patient was suggested the Zhan Zhuang (Embracing the Tree) technique, a breathing technique to tonify the body. Performed while seated with legs shoulder-width apart, the arms are placed as if embracing a tree in front of the navel. The patient is instructed to perform slow, deep, and abdominal breaths, inhaling and exhaling through the nose with the tongue touching the roof of the mouth²⁷. Studies associate this practice with a reduction in anxiety and cognitive improvement^{27,28}.

3.4. Phytotherapy (Chinese Herbal Medicine)

Phytotherapy is one of the main therapeutic modalities of Traditional Chinese Medicine, used for thousands of years to promote energy balance and treat functional imbalances in the body. It is based on the use of medicinal plants, individually or in formulas. From a Traditional Chinese Medicine perspective, plants can tonify *Qi*, *Yin*, *Yang* or Blood, eliminate pathogenic factors such as wind, heat, cold and dampness, as well as harmonise the *Zang Fu*.

The selection of the formulas was made in a personalised manner, respecting the patient's constitution, the predominant energetic pattern, and possible interactions with conventional medication in use.

To improve cerebral blood flow, memory, and attention, with an antioxidant and neuroprotective effect, the intake of *Ginkgo biloba* was recommended²⁹.

For the anti-inflammatory and antioxidant action, with studies suggesting an increase in neurotrophins, promoting neuronal protection, the intake of Nettle (*Urtica dioica*) was suggested³⁰.

To modulate neurotransmitters related to memory, and for a calming action on the *Shen*, the intake of Liquorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) was indicated³¹.

To improve circulation, regulate the spleen and stomach, with antioxidant activity, the intake of Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) was recommended⁷. Table 3 shows the Traditional Chinese Medicine perspective on this custom formulation.

Table 3. Custom phytotherapy formulation.

Ingredient	Taste and temperature	Meridians entered
<i>Ginkgo biloba</i>	Sweet, Bitter, Pungent, neutral	Heart and Lung
<i>Urtica dioica</i>	Bitter, Pungent, cold	Liver
<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	Sweet, neutral	Heart, Lung, Spleen, and Stomach
<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	Pungent, warm	Spleen, Stomach and Lung

This formulation is characterised by a balancing thermal nature, three pungent ingredients to disperse and promote circulation of *Qi* and blood, two bitter ingredients to drain heat and toxins, and two sweet ingredients to tonify the body and harmonise all the ingredients, diminishing possible adverse effects.

The patient should boil the ingredients in a minimum of one litre of water. The mixture should be consumed throughout the day to concomitantly ensure better hydration. It would be best to avoid consuming this beverage within two hours of taking conventional medication.

3.5. Diet Therapy

Diet therapy, as a fundamental component of Traditional Chinese Medicine, consists of using food as a therapeutic medium to promote health, prevent diseases, and restore the body's energetic balance. Based on the principles of *Yin-Yang*, the five elements, and the meridians, diet therapy seeks to harmonise physiological functions and strengthen internal organs through the proper selection of foods, considering their energetic properties, flavours, and effects on the body³²⁻³⁴. This integrative perspective allows for the personalisation of dietary plans according to the patient's clinical state, contributing to a holistic and complementary approach to conventional treatments³⁵.

Based on Traditional Chinese Medicine theory related to nourishing *Yin* and preserving bodily fluids, fresh, easily digestible foods with a high water content were recommended, such as steamed fruits and vegetables. At the same time, the patient was advised to reduce the consumption of fried and grilled foods and spicy condiments. Additionally, the moderate intake of neutral and warm flavours was suggested, aiming to strengthen the Kidney and Essence³⁶. These recommendations are detailed in Table 4.

Table 4. Recommendations characteristics.

Thermal Nature	Food Group	Therapeutic Function in Traditional Chinese Medicine
Neutral	Cereals: Brown rice, barley; Legumes: Adzuki beans; Vegetables: Chinese cabbage, shiitake mushrooms; Fruits: Pear, apple (cooked); Proteins: White fish, cooked eggs; Seaweed/Oilseeds: Kombu seaweed, black sesame seeds; Beverages: Chrysanthemum tea, warm water.	Nourish fluids and <i>Yin</i> , strengthen the spleen-stomach, and calm the <i>Shen</i> .
	Cereals: Quinoa, oats; Legumes: Lentils, chickpeas; Vegetables: Pumpkin, carrot, sweet potato; Fruits: Black grape, fig; Proteins: Cooked organic chicken, freshwater fish; Oilseeds: Walnuts; Beverages: Licorice decoction, gentle ginger infusion.	Tonify <i>Qi</i> and blood without generating excessive heat, slightly warm the centre, and support the kidney and essence.

4. Results and Discussion

Over the course of the 10-session treatment and as indicated by the self-evaluation questionnaire, the patient demonstrated significant clinical improvement. The patient reported a substantial reduction in anxiety, chest pressure, and a near-elimination of morning headaches. His mental clarity and focus improved. Although he still experienced minor forgetfulness, he was able to use compensatory strategies effectively.

A notable achievement was the improvement in emotional management, with reduced irritability and a more compassionate self-attitude. He also reported a decrease in disturbing dreams, which was associated with greater emotional stability.

The synergistic action of the combined therapies was a key factor in the positive outcome. Acupuncture was crucial for rebalancing *Yin* and containing *Yang*, while *Tui Na* and *Qigong* contributed to the continuity of therapeutic effects between sessions. The phytotherapy and diet therapy reinforced the nourishment of the body and mind, aligning with the overall goal of addressing the root cause of the symptoms.

Ageing, although a natural process, can imply energetic changes that impact the individual's overall health. Since this process is linked to the decline of *Jing* and the functional decrease of the Kidneys, Heart, Liver, and Spleen^{5,6}. In the analysed case, the physical and emotional symptoms reflect chronic energetic imbalances, with associated deficiencies and stagnations. Traditional Chinese Medicine proposes an integrative approach that aims to restore energetic balance and promote well-being in old age through therapies such as acupuncture, phytotherapy, diet therapy, and *Qigong*^{6,10}. This intervention demonstrated clinical benefits, suggesting the potential of Traditional Chinese Medicine in promoting a more harmonious ageing process¹². Future studies with larger samples and validated instruments are recommended to consolidate these results.

As Maciocia²⁴ states, "A serene mind is a reflection of a well-nourished heart and a firm essence", reinforcing the importance of caring for the *Shen* and *Jing* throughout the ageing process.

5. Conclusion

This case study illustrates the potential of an integrative Traditional Chinese Medicine approach to manage the physical and emotional symptoms of ageing. The combination of acupuncture, *Tui Na*, *Qigong*, phytotherapy, and diet therapy showed significant clinical benefits for the patient, particularly in addressing anxiety, cognitive clarity, and headaches. While these results are promising, it is important to acknowledge that this is a single case study. Future research with larger, controlled trials is needed to validate these

findings and formally establish the role of Traditional Chinese Medicine in promoting a healthier and more harmonious ageing process.

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